

The Intersection of Social Worker and Healthcare: Challenges and Opportunities in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area

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Abstract

This study investigated the challenges social workers face in medical institutions; a study of government teaching hospitals in Obia/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State. Primary source of data was generated through self-administered questionnaires. The population of the study was 800 medical staffs, while the sample size of 267 was determined using the Taro Yamane's formula for sample size determination. The study involved different cadres of hospital staff including; clinicians, nurses, radiologists, dental officers and hospital nutritionist. The study concludes that these challenges are the source of under-utilization of the medical social workers, which affects the welfare of patients and clients who would otherwise have benefited from social welfare officers interventions. The present paper is on the roles and functions of social workers should be made known in the hospital through the promotion of information about the discipline by its practitioners in the hospital.

Introduction

Hospital-based social workers play a vital role in the adult healthcare system. These dedicated professionals possess a unique set of skills, providing crucial support and assistance to patients and their families during an especially challenging time. With mounting pressure to accelerate discharges and free up more hospital beds, hospital social workers are stretched to capacity. Inefficient technology and convoluted administration systems also leave them with less time to provide individualised social and emotional support for patients who need it. Hospital social workers have multi-dimensional roles. They are a crucial part of delivering person-centred care in hospital settings, ensuring that patients receive appropriate care and support. Social workers **advocate** for a patient's right to individual and personalised care, and provide practical and emotional support during difficult circumstances. They help patients and their families understand and come to terms with the impact of illness, disability, treatments, or deaths. Hospital social workers see the whole person, not just the reason for admission. They understand that patients are more than just a broken hip or respiratory case – they are people

with unique characteristics, circumstances, and care needs. This often means gaining the trust of a patient to truly understand their background, navigating complex family dynamics and opposing wishes, and fighting for the best interests of the patient – while also balancing the targets and procedures set by their employers. Hospital social workers may also be involved in Deprivation of Liberty Safeguards (DoLS) and ensuring the patient is protected across all accounts. Effective communication and collaboration among multi-disciplinary teams, patients and families is crucial for successful discharge planning. However, ensuring that everyone involved is informed, engaged, and working toward the same goals can be a tricky task that delays discharge. These are some of the communication barriers we encounter most often:

- Lack of standardised communication protocols.
- Limited availability of multi-disciplinary meetings.
- Difficulty in accessing relevant patient information.
- Insufficient opportunities for collaboration between healthcare teams.

The multicultural nature of the UK population poses unique challenges for hospital-based social workers who will often encounter patients with language barriers, cultural differences, and healthcare beliefs very different to their own. Social workers are already trained to be empathetic listeners and communicators, but navigating these challenges is a delicate art that takes additional time and resources – which often aren't available. Social workers in hospitals often have large caseloads, juggling multiple patients with varying needs and complexities. This can lead to time constraints, making it a challenge to provide the comprehensive level of support each individual needs. Time-consuming bureaucratic and administrative tasks can also eat up a social worker's time, especially if the technology is outdated and requires keying in multiple times. This leaves professionals with even less time to spend with their patients.

Research Aim and Objectives

Understand the challenges the social workers face in medical institutions

Research Question.

What are the challenges the social workers face in medical institutions?

Scope of the Study

For the sake of time and limited resources this paper seeks to investigate the challenges facing integration of social work professionals into medical institutions in Obio-Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. The study will primarily focus on the health care delivery of medical social welfare department of University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH), as this is part of the Government Teaching Hospital in Obio-Akpor LGA with a functional social work department. Also, the researcher seeks to understand the level of awareness of social work services among health workers.

Significance of the Study

This study seeks to add to the existing knowledge in social work literature, therefore, this study will be of ultimate importance to students seeking to develop their knowledge in the discipline and all social workers in any specialty, including; family social work, medical social work, social work with the elderly, social work with people in crisis, social work intervention with the vulnerable population.

It is also the aim of the researcher to influence government policy through this research paper, therefore this study serves as an eye opener to the happenings in the society some are known while others are unknown by the government officers.

The study is designed to serve as a secondary source of data in social work research; this simply means the study is meant to aid researchers in carrying out their work. The medical practitioners such as the physicians, nurses, psychiatrist seeking to develop their knowledge of the need of the roles social workers in medical setting can also find this study interesting.

The research is also being carried out in partial fulfillment of the requirement of a degree in Bachelor of Science in Social Work (BSW), this simply means that the research is equally helpful to the researcher.

Limitations

The research only focused on Government Teaching Hospitals in Obia/Akpor LGA in Rivers State. Hence, the findings may not be adequate in generalizing it to cover other medical institutions. The second factor is that there is a wide geographical scope of Hospitals in Rivers State which was difficult to visit all which may affect conclusion and generalization of findings. Another major limitation is that the respondent of this study are medical workers who have little or no time for activities outside their working schedule. Hence, the retrieval of questionnaire was greatly as only 215 out of 267 questionnaires that were distributed were retrieved.

Definition of Terms

Social Worker

Within the United States, a social worker is an individual who possesses a baccalaureate or master's degree in social work from a school or program accredited by the Council on Social Work Education. Although all 50 states and the District of Columbia license or certify social workers, licensure and certification laws vary by state. Each social worker should be licensed or certified, as applicable and required, at the level appropriate to her or his scope of practice in the practitioner's jurisdiction(s).

Client

Client refers to the “individual, group, family, or community that seeks or is provided with professional services” (Barker, 2013, p. 73). For purposes of these standards, the term “client” refers to an individual. The term “patient” is more commonly used by social workers employed in health care settings.

Biopsychosocial–Spiritual Perspective

A biopsychosocial–spiritual perspective recognizes the importance of whole person care and takes into account a client’s physical or medical condition; emotional or psychological state; socioeconomic, sociocultural, and sociopolitical status; and spiritual needs and concerns.

Bioethics

Bioethics is “the analysis and study of legal, moral, social, and ethical considerations involving the biological and medical sciences” (Barker, 2013).

Case Management

Case management is a collaborative process to plan, seek, advocate for, and monitor services, resources, and supports on behalf of a client. Case management enables a health care social worker to serve clients who may require the services of various health care providers and facilities, community-based organizations, social services agencies, and other programs.

Research Aim and Objectives

- (i) Identify staff awareness on the presence of social work professionals in the hospital

Research Questions

(i) What is the level of staff awareness on the presence of social work professionals in the hospital?

Scope of the Study

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Significance of the Study

The study aimed at identifying challenges facing integration of social work professionals into medical cadre. The identified challenges shall be communicated to the Ministry of Social Welfare and Rehabilitation Centre and the heads of department to make them understand the existing challenges facing integration of social work professionals into medical practice. The results of this research study can help in developing strategies on how to eliminate those challenges hence maximize the benefits to clients who require social workers interventions. This study will assist to create awareness to the local government authority on the need to strengthen the social welfare department in terms of allocating adequate funds as well as increasing the number of social workers into medical practice. Moreover, on job programs might be designed to orient all staff on the roles and functions of social workers into medical practice including cases required to be attended by social workers.

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Meaning and definition of social work

The social work industry developed in the 19th century, with some of its roots in voluntary philanthropy and in grassroots organizing (Dorrien. G.2011). However, responses to social needs had existed long before then, primarily from private charities and from religious

organizations. The effects of the Industrial Revolution and of the Great Depression of the 1930s placed pressure on social work to become a more defined discipline.

Challenges that Social Workers Encounter in Practice

Social workers are employed in a variation of fields, organizational settings, and work with a diverse population. Regardless of the practice area social workers have demanding jobs. Due to the high demands of the profession, social workers are at high risk for burnout (Kim, Ji, & Kao, 2011). One report found that challenges social workers encounter included increasing paperwork, unmanageable caseloads, and difficult clients (Whitaker et al., 2006). Social workers report that major work-related stressors included insufficient time to do their job, large number of cases, and dealing with challenging clients (Whitaker & Arrington, 2008).

Insufficient Time

According to Whitaker and Arrington (2008) lack of time to do their job was the highest work-related stressor reported among social workers. Social workers report that they are not given adequate time to complete work-related tasks. With increases in their clientele's severity of problems and increases in paperwork it is clear that lack of time is a major stressor for social workers (Whitaker et al., 2006). This can potentially have a negative impact on clients as more time will be focused on paper work rather than invested in attending to the needs of the clients.

Large Number of Cases

Heavy caseloads are common in the field of social work; this is especially true for social workers in the field of child welfare. Social workers are often given caseloads that exceed the recommended maximum which puts substantial pressure on the worker to process their cases as quickly as possible (Yamatani, Engel, & Spjeldnes, 2009). The quick processing of cases can negatively impact clients as social workers are unable to provide adequate time and services needed for each case.

Challenging Clients

Social workers report that dealing with challenging clients is one of the major challenges they experience that lead to increases in stress, this is especially true of social workers providing mental health services (Whitaker & Arrington, 2008). Acker and Lawrence (2009) found that social workers who work with clients that have severe and persistent mental illnesses reported feeling incompetent, which led to higher levels of burnout symptoms. Ethical dilemmas can also arise when dealing with difficult clients. Ulrich et al. (2007) found that nearly two-thirds of social workers reported that they felt powerless, overwhelmed, and frustrated when there were presented with ethical issues that they could not do anything about. This can negatively impact clients as it can lead to inadequate and unethical services to clients.

Structural and Functional Problem

According to Breakwell & Rowen (2002) for a human organization to achieve a high degree of congruity between its actual structure and functions and how these would be perceived by outsiders, the following conditions should pertain;

(i) There should be general consensus among members about its structure and functions;

(ii) There should exist organizational and professional functions acceptable to the general public and;

(iii) There should be organizational readiness and capacity to cultivate a receptive public image, especially where the media is concerned. It is argued that social work does not adequately meet these criteria

Firstly, with regard to its structure and functions, social work is an amorphous, ill-defined profession (Bar-On, 2004). It is not a homogeneous occupational category. As indicated previously, social workers are employed in a wide variety of statutory, voluntary and private agencies and settings. However, this reality is generally not well known, particularly in the African context. Furthermore, because social welfare agencies are not properly coordinated and integrated, this creates a lot of disharmony and conflict.

Secondly, there seems to be widespread confusion among social workers themselves about the direction in which they are or should be moving. There is disagreement about what they should be doing and how they should be doing it. To a considerable extent, confusion and disagreement stem from the fact that while performing their tasks, social workers use certain methods and techniques which are neither readily understandable nor acceptable to the other helping professions and the public at large. Besides, there is little agreement over the type and nature of the complaints which social workers ought or should be dealing with, given the intractability and ambiguity that characterize social problems.

In the light of the above, it is understandable why the role of social workers is not sufficiently recognized. The average social worker, especially in the African context lacks credibility. She/he has yet to demonstrate that she/he is a trusted and helpful friend. The non-recognition of social workers may explain why so many social problems are taken to the courts, district

commissioners, priests and witchdoctors. Needless to say, the non-recognition of social work tends to discourage and demoralize practitioners as well as those who might be interested in pursuing careers in this field.

Thirdly, social work has failed to effectively articulate its goals, functions and techniques. Hence, the mismatches between the rather distorted public imagery of social work on the one hand and its real image on the other. The perception of social work by the media, the public and other professions, is not only variable but also biased in the way it portrays the profession's structure, functions and dynamics. To compound the problem, social workers as an occupational grouping, are not sufficiently united. They have not been able to develop a collective, coherent, vigorous voice to articulate their role and interests and boost their prestige and status.

The existing so-called National Associations of Social Workers (NASW) are not only fragmented organizationally and strategically, but also they represent only a small proportion of the potential membership (Breakwell&Rowett, 1982).

Lack of professionally-trained social workers is a major constraint on social work in Africa. This problem can be partly attributed to inadequate financial support for social welfare programs. Owing to chronic recession, conservative ideologies and misguided policies, many African governments, like their counterparts in America and Europe, have been advocating reduced spending on social welfare. There is a widespread belief that investment in social welfare programs does not contribute, at least directly, to economic growth and development. On the other hand, economic development programs tend to receive a lion's share of government funding, which makes it difficult for social welfare agencies to obtain the necessary human and material resources to implement their programs (Macpherson, 2008).

Scarcity of financial resources means inadequate office facilities and supplies (filing cabinets, stationery and tape recorders). Under such conditions, keeping records and confidentiality becomes highly problematic. Moreover, shortage of funds means inadequate transport and communication facilities which in turn implies that home visits cannot be easily or efficiently made, especially in relation to clients residing in rural areas where the bulk of the population lives.

Social work is one of the most overworked, underpaid, under-recognized and distressed professions. As Ankrah (2001) points out, lack of recognition by governments manifests itself in the lower levels of remuneration and status accorded to social workers compared to other professionals with similar qualifications. As a result, social workers are very vulnerable to stress-generating situations such as roleoverload, role-conflict, role-ambiguity, over-responsibility, and poor working conditions. These stressors tend to cause burnout, which refers to the depletion of the social worker's physical and psychological resources, mainly associated with a desire to achieve, unrealistic expectations and powerlessness.

Many social workers in Africa are finding it difficult to handle work-related stress, resulting in frustration and reduced efficiency. To a great extent, the trials and tribulations facing social work today can be blamed on the fact that the sociopolitical milieu in many African societies is not yet conducive to facilitate radical forms of intervention. The main impediment is the political leaders' narrow and conservative conception of the role and function of social work. Midgley (2007) assertively argues that:

...developing countries' political elites have no intention of redistributing income and wealth to eradicate mass poverty. They use social work as a palliative and as a means of camouflaging the material basis of deprivation.

The consequence of this constricted perception of social work is that in many African countries social work does not proactively address structural sources of poverty but only functions as a passive and unambitious distributor of meager means-tested food hand-outs which effectively keep clients in the vicious cycle of poverty. It is the view of some writers that African governments should elevate social work to the role of a dynamic agent and manager of change. For example, Khinduka (2001) is optimistic that if developing countries can constructively engage social work in development, significant structural change and socioeconomic improvements can be achieved. Obviously, for a change in this direction to come to pass the traditional approach which attaches overriding emphasis on economic development at the expense of social development (Midgley, 2007; Macpherson & Midgley, 2008) should be transformed.

The Role of Social Workers In Discharge Planning

For many hospital-based social workers in the UK, assisting patients with post-hospital care arrangements has become their main task. By taking the lead in discharge planning, social workers aim to smooth the transition from hospital to home, ensuring patients can safely function in their usual environment. Their work helps reduce the number of readmissions – freeing up more hospital beds and easing pressure on health services. Social workers work to address the unique needs of each patient, employing a holistic approach that includes the expertise of medical professionals while also considering the availability and accessibility of community-based services. The role of social services within discharge planning involves three key stages:

1. Comprehensive assessment of the patient's individual needs. Practitioners carry out detailed assessments, including care needs, mental health, risk factors, and more.
2. Formulating an appropriate and safe discharge plan. Social workers coordinate discharge planning with nurses, doctors and community resources to ensure the patient's care needs will be met once they leave hospital. This includes a plan for reablement, if required. Social workers plan in conjunction with occupational therapists

to determine the appropriate equipment or home adaptations necessary to create a safe and comfortable environment.

3. Implementing the plan in a timely manner. Once patients are medically fit, their care plan should already be in place to allow them to safely leave hospital – whether this is to return home, or to move to longer term residential care.

Research Method

The Study Area

The study was conducted at University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH) Port Harcourt. The area is selected as one of the government hospitals with social work professionals working with other medical field practitioners.

Research Design

Nachimias (2003) defined research design as “the blue print that enables the investigators to come up with solutions to problems and guide him/her in the various stages of the research. This study adopts a descriptive cross sectional survey. Cross-sectional surveys are studies aimed at determining the frequency or level of a particular attribute in a defined population at a particular point in time. A cross sectional study is commonly used in medical and social science researches. A cross sectional study or prevalence study is the type of observational study that involves the analysis of data collected from a population or representative subset at one specific point in time. The data were collected using questionnaires which were given to respondents and the analysis of the collected data portrayed the factors that challenge integration of social work professionals in medical services.

Population of the Study

According to Nachimias (2003) population is defined as “the aggregate of all cases that conform to some designated set of specification. Kombo and Tromp (2006) defined population as the largest group from which the sample is taken. The population of the study comprises all the medical staffs of the University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital working with social welfare department in the hospital which is about 800 in number. This number was obtained from the human resource department of the hospital.

Sampling Techniques and Sample Size

Nachimias (2003) defined sample as “the sub set of a population”. Thus, in view of the fact that our study involves a finite population, a sample size that can be possibly reached is obtained. Kothari (2004) defined sampling techniques or procedure as “a definite plan for obtaining a sample for population given. The study sample size was arrived at using the Taro Yamen’s 1970 formula.

The sample size was calculated by using the Taro Yamen Sample size determination formula;

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Whereby; n=Sample size, N= total population (800) and e= an acceptable error (0.05).

$$\text{Therefore } n = \frac{800}{1+800(0.05)^2} = 266.7$$

In this research study the sample size was 267.

Data Collection Method

Questionnaire

The questionnaire involves a set of questions to collect information from subjects on their perceptions, feelings to the subject under study. It helps in providing accurate data that are quantifiable easily. The study which is dominantly quantitative in nature, adopts the structured questionnaire in the generation of primary data for the study. Copies of questionnaire would be personally administered, followed up and retrieved.

Data Analysis Approach

Braun and Clarke (2006) state that “thematic analysis is a qualitative analytic method for identifying, analyzing and reporting patterns within data. Thematic analysis minimally organizes and described data set in details. However, it goes further than this and interprets various aspect of the research topic. Data collected from the field were structured to ensure consistency of responses. Data generated were arranged and coded according to themes and then fed into the data editor section of Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS 21.0). Analysis were undertaken in two phases beginning with the demographic profile, using percentages, describes the frequencies of responses to various sample characteristics. Secondly the research questions and findings were analyzed through mean scores and standard deviations.

Validity of the Instrument

According to Babbie (2007), the term validity refers to the extent to which an empirical measure adequately reflects the real meaning of the concept under consideration. Validity is defined as the ability of the scale to measure what it is designed or purported to measure. For validity of the measurement to be established, there should be a complete absence of

measurement error. It is important that a reliability and validity test be carried out comprehensively at every stage of the research work. Babbie (2007) posit that, after operationalizing, defining variables and applying different scaling techniques, it is pertinent to ensure that each research instrument employed be adequately tested for reliability and validity. In this study, the researcher ensured that the measure for reliability included an adequate and effective representative set of items that tap the concept. Serious effort was made to ensure that the scale items represented the domain or universe of the concept being measured. In other words, the measurement is a function of how well the dimensions and indicators of the various concepts are been delineated, which logically reflected the study variables. The validation of the instrument would be ensured through my supervisors vetting. Through this process, errors in the questionnaire such as ambiguity, contradictory questions, poor wording of questions, misleading or poor instructions among others would be detected and eliminated.

Tests of Reliability of Instrument

Reliability is the ability of a measuring instrument to achieve consistent results each time it is adopted. However, Nunnally (1979) asserts that the reliability alpha values in determining the internal consistency of the instrument should maintain a minimum threshold of 0.7. Based on this, the Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient method was utilized in this study since it is the most predominant method of testing reliability in social sciences research (Hair, Black, Babin& Anderson 2010).

Data Presentation, Analysis and Discussion of Findings

Table 1 Educational Qualification of Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Doctoral Degree	35	17.1	17.1	17.1
Master's Degree	20	9.8	9.8	26.8
Bachelor/HND	115	56.1	56.1	82.9

NCE	3	1.5	1.5	84.4
Others	32	15.6	15.6	100.0
Total	205	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Work (2019)

Figure 1: bar chart showing educational qualification of respondents

The data in table 1 portrays the educational level and qualification distribution of the respondents. From the results above, 34 respondents indicating 16.6 percent of the respondents were Doctoral Degree holders, 24 respondents indicating 11.7 percent of the respondents are Master’s Degree holders, 113 respondents indicating 55.1 percent of the respondents were BSc/HND holders, 3 respondents indicating 1.5 percent of the respondents have NCE, while 31 respondent representing 15.1 had other certificates.

Analysis of Research Question

Research Question: What are the challenges the social workers face in medical institutions

Table 2 Response Rates on the staff awareness on the challenges of social work professionals in the hospital

	Challenges the social workers	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean	Std.
1	The social work unit in the hospital is under-staff	55	92	7	25	26	3.61	1.33721
2	The social workers in the hospital have less time and more workload	49	73	7	53	23	3.35	1.38038
3	The social workers in the hospital are not allowed to take decisions affecting their own profession	70	42	4	63	26	3.33	1.51318
4	There are less resources for social workers to carry out their intervention in the hospital	48	106	9	27	15	3.71	1.17665
5	Social workers are provided with less facilities to carry out their duty in the hospital	43	110	10	33	9	3.71	1.10356

Source: Research Survey Data, 2019

The result of table 2 reveals that all items (1-5) have mean scores above 2.50. The statement ‘There are less resources for social workers to carry out their intervention in the hospital’ has the highest mean score (M=3.71; SD=1.17665) followed by ‘Social workers are provided with less facilities to carry out their duty in the hospital’ (M=3.71SD=1.10356), ‘The social work unit in the hospital is under-staff’ (M=3.61;SD=1.33721), ‘The social workers in the hospital have less time and more workload’ (M=3.35;SD=1.38038), ‘The social workers in the hospital are not allowed to take decisions affecting their own profession’ (M=3.33;SD=1.51318). This show all the items indicate that social workers are facing a lot challenges in the hospital. This is true since the mean values are above the benchmark of 2.5, meaning that most of the respondents were on the agree range of the scale. Thus it is clear that social worker unit in the

hospital is understaffed, has less time and more workload, have less resources to intervene in the case of indecency, and also less facilities to carry out their task in the hospital.

Discussion of findings

These result shows that social workers in the hospital are facing serious challenges which need urgent attention of both the ministry of health and the ministry of social welfare and rehabilitation. Hence it is the desire of the researcher to unveil these challenges as it seriously affects the well-being of patients in the hospital. Secondly, the result also shows that social work intervention is facing a lot of limitation in the government hospitals in Rivers state, and apart from lack of awareness of roles and cases that need social work intervention, this noble profession is facing other challenge which are unknown to the public.

Recommendations

- i.** The roles and functions of social workers should be made known in the hospital through the promotion of information about the discipline by its practitioners in the hospital
- ii.** Social workers should contribute in the development of strategies that will assist in the development of the profession
- iii.** Social workers should be provided with enough facilities to enable them provide more support to the patients in the hospital.
- iv.** Social work as a professional discipline functions well with its ethics and principle, therefore, its practitioners should be allowed to take decision within its jurisdiction.

Reference

- Ankrah, E. M. (2001). "Social Work Uganda: Survival in the Midst of Turbulence," in Hokenstad, M.; Khinduka, S. & Midgley, J. Profiles in International Social Work, Washington, DC: NASW Press.
- Anucha, U., (2008). Exploring a New Direction for Social Work Education and Training in Nigeria. *Social Work Education*. 27. 229-242. 10.1080/02615470701381459.
- Babbie, E. (2007) *The practice of social research*. 11th Edition, Thompson Wadsworth, Belmont.
- Bar-On, A. A. (2004). "The Elusive Boundaries of Social Work," *Journal of Sociology and Social Welfare*, 21(3), 53-67.
- Barker, M. (2013), Anaesthetic emergencies. *Veterinary Nursing Journal*, 28: 220-224. doi:10.1111/vnj.12047
- Barr, M. S. (2004). *Banking the poor: Policies to bring low-income Americans into the financial mainstream*. Washington, D.C.: Brookings Institution.
- Blyton, P. & Turnbull, P. (1992), 'HRM: Debates, Dilemmas and Contradictions', in P. Blyton & P. Turnbull (eds), *Reassessing Human Resource Management*, London: Sage, Publications Inc.
- Birkenmaier, J., & Curley, J., (2009). "Financial credit: Social work's role in empowering low-income families". *Journal of Community Practice*. 17(3):251–268.
- Braun, V., and Clarke, V. (2006). *Using the thematic analysis in psychology*. Qualitative research in psychology, 3(2), 77-101. London: Routledge.
- Breakwell, G. M. & Rowell, C. (2002). *Social Work: The Social Psychological Approach*, Berkshire: Van Nostrand Reinhold Co.
- Breakwell, G. M. & Rowell, C. (2002). *Social Work: The Social Psychological Approach*, Berkshire: Van Nostrand Reinhold Co.
- Breakwell, G. M., & Rowett, C. (1982). *Social Work: The Social Psychological Approach*. Wokingham, U. K.: Van Nostrand Reinhold.

Canadian Association of Social Workers "What is Social Work?" www.casw-acts.ca. Retrieved May 13, 2019.

Canadian Association of Social Workers "What is Social Work?" www.casw-acts.ca. Retrieved July 17, 2019.

Canadian Association of Social Workers "What is Social Work?" www.casw-acts.ca. Retrieved July 19, 2019.

Child, J. (1969). *British Management Thought: A Critical Analysis*, London: George Allen & Unwin.

[Charity Organization Societies: 1877-1893 - Social Welfare History Project](#)". *Social Welfare History Project*. February 4, 2013. Retrieved December 29, 2017.

Crisp, B.R., & Beddoe, L., (2012). *Promoting Health and Well-being in Social Work Education*. Routledge.

Despard, M., & Chowa, G.A.N., (2010). "Social workers' interest in building individuals' financial capabilities". *Journal of Financial Therapy*. 1 (1): 23–41.

Digestive Program". *Current Problems in Pediatric and Adolescent Health Care*. 48 (4): 111–112.

[Dorrien, G., \(2011\) . "Fostering Democratic Citizenship: Jane Addams". Social Ethics in the Making: Interpreting an American Tradition. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons. p. 168. ISBN 9781444393798](#). Retrieved May 13, 2019.

Dunlop, J. T. (1958) *Industrial Relations Systems*. New York: Holt Rinehart and Winston
Fajana, S. (2000) *Industrial Relations in Nigeria: Theory and Features* (2nd Ed.). Lagos: Labofinpublishers

Eysenck, H. J. Charles C. T., (1967). *The biological basis of personality*. Springfield, IL:

Ferdinand Tönnies (ed. Jose Harris), *Community and Civil Society*, Cambridge University Press (2001), hardcover, 266 pages, ISBN 0-521-56119-1; trade paperback, Cambridge University Press (2001), 266 pages, ISBN 0-521-56782-3

Flexner, A., (2018). "Is social work a profession?". New York, The New York school of philanthropy – via Internet Archive.

Fonash, A., (2018). "The Role of the Medical Social Worker in a Pediatric Aero-

Francis J. T., (2005). [Encyclopedia of Canadian Social Work](#). Wilfrid Laurier Univ. Press. pp. 219, 236. [ISBN 978-0-88920-436-2](#).

Fink, C. F. (1968). Some conceptual difficulties in the theory of social conflict. *Journal of Conflict Resolution*, 12(4), 412–460.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/002200276801200402>

Fubara, B.A. and Mguni, B.S (2005) *Research Methods in Management* Port Harcourt, Pear Publishers Pp 50-92.

["Global Definition of Social Work | International Federation of Social Workers".ifsw.org](#). Retrieved July 19, 2017

Grinker, R. R., MacGregor, H., Selan, K., Klein, A., & Kohrman, J., (1961). *Early years of psychiatric social work*. *Social Service Review*, 35, 111–126.

Guest, D. (1989). Human Resource Management: Its Implications for Industrial Relations and Trade Unions', in J. Storey (ed.), *New Perspectives on Human Resource Management*,

Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., & Anderson, R. E. (2010). *Multivariate data analysis*. (7th ed.). Upper Saddle River, New Jersey: Prentice Hall.

Huff, D., (1900) ["Chapter I. Scientific Philanthropy "](#). *The Social Work History Station*. [Boise State University](#). Retrieved February 20, 2008.

International Federation of Social Workers [Global Definition of Social Work](#) ifsw.org. Retrieved May 13, 2019.

Jarrett, M. C. (1918): *Psychiatric social work*. In: *Mental Hygiene* 2, pp. 283-290.

- Keough, M. E; Samuels, M. F., (2004). "The Kosovo Family Support Project:Offering Psychosocial Support for Families with Missing Persons". *Social Work*. 49 (4): 587–594. doi:10.1093/sw/49.4.587.
- Khinduka, S. K. (2001). "Social working the Third World," in *Social Services Review*, 45(4), 62- 72.
- Kirt, J., and Miller, M. L. (1986).*Reliability and Validity in Qualitative Research*. Beverly Hills: Sage Publications Inc.
- Kombo, D. K. and Tromp D. L. A., (2006). *Proposal and Thesis Writing: An introduction*. Nairobi: Pauline’s publications Africa.
- Kothari, C.R. (2004) *Research Methodology: Methods and Techniques*. 2nd Edition, New Age International Publishers, New Delhi.
- Macpherson, S, (1982). *Social Policy in the Third World: The Social Dilemmas of Underdevelopment*, Brighton: Wheatsheaf Books.
- Macpherson, S., &Midgley, J, (2008). *Comparative Social Policy and the Third World*, Brighton: Wheatsheaf Books.
- Maslow, A. H. (1954). *Motivation and personality*. New York: Harper and Row.
- Mayo, E. (1933). *The Human Problems of Industrial Civilization*, New York: Macmillan Company.
- Morris, P. (2008). Reinterpreting Abraham Flexner’s Speech, “Is Social Work a Profession?”: Its Meaning and Influence on the Field’s Early Professional Development. *Social Service Review*, 82(1), 29-60. doi:10.1086/529399
- Murali D. N; Erick G. G., (2014). *Evidence Based Macro Practice in Social Work*. Gregory Publishing Company. ISBN 978-0-911541-94-6.
- Midgley, J. (1981). *Professional Imperialism: Social work the Third World*, London: Heinemann.

Nachimias, J. (2003). *Research methodology in the Social Science*. (5th Ed): London: St. Mart Press Inc.

Nair, U., Yen, W. L., Mari, M., Cao, Y., Xie, Z., Baba, M., ...Klionsky, D. J. (2012). A role for Atg8-PE deconjugation in autophagosome biogenesis. *Autophagy*, 8(5), 780–793. doi:10.4161/auto.19385

National Association of Social Workers "Code of Ethics (English and Spanish)" socialworkers.org. Archived from the original on June 6, 2002.

National Association of Social Workers (NASW), *www.naswdc.org*. Archived from the original on May 31, 2002. Retrieved July 19, 2019.

"National Association of Social Workers".NASW.Retrieved September 6, 2019.

Nunnally, J. C. (1978). *Psychometric theory* (2nd ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill "Ontario College of Social Workers and Social Service Workers: The Centre for Education & Training" (PDF). 2011. Retrieved November 8, 2019

PhyllidaParsole. *Risk assessment in social care and social work*. 2001. Jessica Kingsley Publishers.

Popple, P. R. and Leighninger, L.,(2011) *Social Work, Social Welfare*, American Society. Boston: Allyn& Bacon

Pavesi. M, Devlin N., Hakimi Z., Nazir J., Herdman M., Hoyle C.&Odeyemi I. A. (2013) Understanding the effects on HR-QoL of treatment for overactive bladder: a detailed analysis of EQ-5D clinical trial data for mirabegron, *Journal of Medical Economics*, 16:7, 866-876, DOI: 10.3111/13696998.2013.802240

Reyna VF, Farley F (2006) *Risk and Rationality in Adolescent Decision Making: Implications for Theory, Practice, and Public Policy*. Administrative Affairs and Employment, (1995).Law and employment regulations. Tehran: Administrative Affairs and Employment organization publication. *Journal of Social Science for Policy Implications*, 2(2), 59 – 68.

- Rex A. S., (1995). *Social Work Administration: Dynamic Management and Human Relationships*. Allyn and Bacon. pp. 2–3. ISBN 978-0-13-669037-5.
- Romich, J.; Simmelink, J.; Holt, S. D., (2007). "When working harder does not pay: Low-income working families, tax liabilities, and benefit reductions" (PDF). *Families in Society*. 88 (3): 418–426. doi:10.1606/1044-3894.3651.
- Rwomile, A. and Ratithokwa, L. (2006). *Social work Africa: Issues and challenges*. *Journal of Social Development in Africa* (1996), 11(2), 5-19.
- Samadi Rad, Anvar. (2008). *social work in Iran*. Kayhan. *Journal of Social Science for Policy Implications*, 2(2), 59 - 68
- Standards for Clinical Social Work Practice (2005). Retrieved on 16th November, 2016 from: https://www.socialworkers.org/practice/NASWClinicalSWS_tandards.pdf
- Sherraden, M.; Laux, S. & Kaufman, C., (2007). "Financial education for social workers". *Journal of Community Practice*. 15 (3): 9–36. doi:10.1300/J125v15n03_02.
- Samadi, R. (2008) *Stellar structure and evolution* (488),(2), pp705 – 714
- Steve, M., (2011. ")," *Asian Economic and Social Society*, 1(5), 181-187.
- William, M.M., Daniel, R. Z., Stephen M.J., Searle, E., 2014, *Nucleic Acids Research*, Volume 42, Issue D1, 1 January 2014, Pages D749–D755,
- Yin, R. K. (1994). *Discovering the Future of the Case Study. Method in Evaluation Research*. *Evaluation Practice*, 15(3), 283–290.